

FULL-TIME TEACHER, PART TIME MOTHER: A MIEN OF BALANCING LIFE ROLES

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ABSTRACT

This study explored the experiences of the teachers of Kiamba Central School SPED Center (KCSSC) as full-time teachers and part time mothers. It employed an in-depth interview to gather the responses of all six (6) participants—who are mothers and teachers as well, at KCSSC. The experiences of being full-time teachers and part-time mothers today ally hardships and challenges. The following major themes came out after thematic analysis: Living with the Roles, Sustaining the Roles, Fulfilling the Roles, and Surviving the Roles. These results affirm to the Role-Balance Theory of Fritz Heider (1946) stating that life can be balanced when roles are attended in an evenhanded fashion—that one’s responsibilities or obligations can be addressed one at a time. More so, this study suggests that teacher-mothers may have a planning scheme, may revitalize their persona, continue the passion, and may find recreation so that they may maintain work-life balance. Moreover, time schedule may be looked-upon by the department heads as it may help improve the quality time for each teacher-mothers’ families. Furthermore, it is also recommended that mental-health related seminars and awareness programs be sustained for the welfare of teacher-mothers.

Keywords: *Full-time Teacher; Part Time Mother; Teacher-mothers; Work-life Balance*

INTRODUCTION

There are risks of affecting the mental health of women in their endeavors to be both “good mothers” as well as “good teachers” Baker (2021). Although there are advantages of being a teacher, especially to one’s child, there are also difficulties to face because of bulking schoolwork done even outside school time (Padios Jr. et al., 2022). Therefore,

the overlapping of events affects women's every endeavor and even the time supposedly to be spent well enough (Rose, 2017). In this connection, Baker (2021) also exposed maintaining parallelism of a good mother whilst a good teacher and its negative consequences. Moreover, doing it so, relatively affects the quality of time (Rose, 2017). It is really challenging to fulfill. However, despite array of challenges alike situations resulted to a positive outcome — that career women can still manage to balance work-life (Soelistiyono & Chuan, 2023).

In the country, there is really a positive result of acting out dual roles being teacher-mothers. Various studies signified how work status of parents have been affecting or impacted the scholastic performance of one's children. Jabar et. al (2021) signified the essentiality of parental involvement in relation to children's education are positively affected by the parents' work status. More so, it is fulfilling to know a related study by Bayod et al. (2021) justifying teachers-mothers' ability to manage their hardships—combined work and responsibilities at home and in school, to balance work and family well-being.

Kiamba Central School SPED Center (KCSSC) is by category a large central school located at the heart of Kiamba municipality—one of the astonishing towns and pride of Sarangani. KCSSC houses a total of seventy (70) teaching and non-teaching employees. It constitutes over 93% female teachers who are 91% married and have children who are schooling. Even if there are different positive studies on teacher-mothers' surpassing their issues and problems in life, teacher-mothers of KCSSC also have different experiences relating to the fulfillment of their duties at home and in school. So, the researchers wanted to find out their specific experiences being full-time teachers and part time mothers and, on their coping-up mechanisms on balancing work-life despite their dual roles. Mothers of the same uniforms with different stories to tell and attest how a full-time teacher as a part-time mother evolves in this era.

This study aimed to understand and scrutinize the unseen reasons why some teachers of today seemed to have less time to mingle socially but managed to provide for their family's well-being and sustenance. More so, this study may bring awareness to policymakers of the Department of Education on the veiled mien and truth behind their teachers' everyday effort of wholly rearing Filipino children.

Research Questions

This study wants to unveil the lived experiences of teachers as teacher-mothers and even their way of maintaining work-life balance. Consequently, the researchers sought answers to the following questions:

1. What are the experiences of the participants being full-time teachers and part time mothers?
2. How do they maintain work-life balance despite their dual roles?

METHODOLOGY

This study used phenomenological qualitative type of research. Qualitative research gathers participants' experiences, perceptions, and behavior (Tenny et al., 2022). It is anchored to the Role-balance theory of Fritz Heider (1946) as the study lens. It is descriptive research that involved inquiry-based approach through utilizing an in-depth interview with the participants. After collecting all data of this phenomena, data analysis was then applied and interpreted to come up with related themes from the expositions gathered. Participants selected were six (6) teacher-mothers working at Kiamba Central School SPED Center (KCSSC) with respective codenames assigned for each of them to conceal their identities.

RESULTS

Experiences of Teacher-Mothers

There are common and uncommon experiences heaved-out from the Participants' expositions. It mirrors similarities of strife and the determination that brings forth everyday survival which firmly compacted to teacher-mothers' concept of real life. Responsibilities of being a full-time teacher versus worries of being a part-time mother were revealed.

Table 1

Experiences of Full-Time Teachers and Part Time Mothers

	Major Themes	Core Ideas	Frequency of Responses
Full-time Teachers	Living with the Roles	Ally Challenges	General
		Heads for Priorities	Typical
	Sustaining the Roles	Availing Benefits	General
Part time Mothers	Fulfilling the Roles	Balancing Work and Family Responsibilities	General
	Surviving the Roles	Strategizing	Typical

Table 1 depicts how the participants experience being full-time teachers and part-time mothers. Hence the themes presented here are out from the context of these participants' daily work-life experiences.

Work-Life Balance of Teachers with Dual Roles

What it is in teacher-mothers' life that it needed equilibrium to maintain balance on different aspects of one's life? Surprisingly, teacher-mothers of today, regardless of years in position and family background, can be viewed as career women who are more on the

side of work performance accomplishments over various roles that awaits them, in majority. It can be supported with several statements that challenges and hardships in and out the school can be strategized but it never meant rediverting one’s profession to ease the life’s hustle of such.

Table 2
Work-Life Balance of Teachers with Dual Roles

Major Themes	Core Ideas	Frequency of Responses
Planning	Avoiding Cramming	General
Revitalizing the Persona	Strengthening Faith in God	Typical
Continuing the Passion	Loving What They Do	Typical
Finding Recreation	Bonding with Friends	Typical

Table 2 shows the consolidated themes brought out from the expositions of the participants on the matters of maintaining work-life balance. These themes present a consolidated revelations on how full-time teachers and part time mothers are balancing their life roles. Regardless of years in service and family background, their experiences can be analytically themed into four. The themes are inclined with how Giroux (2019) emphasized about career women as teacher-mothers implore strategize and be resilient on attending work—including its complexities.

DISCUSSION

Full-time Teachers

The main heading full-time teachers signify the current experiences exposed by the participants on the context of how teachers today juggle up to meet their ends. This section reveals about all the hidden strategies teacher-mothers are practicing so that they can surmount all the hardships and bulk of works relating to the profession they are in. Full-time teachers in the context of these participants are particularly focused on their goals that no matter what happens, the focus in on accomplishing their workloads and provide for their family’s well-being.

Living with the Roles

A teacher-mother does not stop solely with being a teacher or a mother. Living as such meant responding to several roles that are to be attended to, responsibly. That is why it is inevitable that living with the roles as teacher-mothers ally struggles and strategies for a better positive result in the incoming days. In addition, out of all the positive gains of being one, there always a constant of negativities in living a such and it is part of balance. **Ally Challenges.** The first core idea can be anchored to the statements of Rose (2017) and Hardin and Pennell (2022), respectively saying that career women surely encounter

time pressure as she aims for work efficacy and maintain family well-being; and how teacher-mothers balance motherhood and work—thus keep the pace. This may be agreed upon by the statements of Mam-A:

“So, for me, it’s [ahh] difficult to balance my time—especially for my children who are now in school. So, I need to look after their assignments—especially their projects and I cannot [ahh] go through with their activities. Because we have different school[s]. Like my eldest son. If he needs my presence, I cannot go there immediately.” (lines 15-16,18)

To be a teacher and a mother do not connote positivity at all. Obviously, even thinking outside the box of the context of my participants, it really deals with so much that challenges our being as a person, and our totality. This portion will entail all the details regarding the challenges and hardships, I should say, that one may encounter in life.

Heads for Priorities. Each of us has our unique way of performing unnoticed multiple roles in life. Each of us has hidden life strategies so our life is spent in balance and in harmony. It is one of the strategies purposively to live with complex roles in balance.

Mam-E’s experience of having to find satisfaction and diversion from being a plain housewife to being a full-time teacher and part time mother contradicts to Hamplová’s (2019) statement saying, “there is happiness among women who shifted from work to homemaking. Because she found even more peace of mind having to dedicate herself to work for her to forget her life’s cruxes.

On the other hand, Mam-B and Mam-E’s experiences on focusing on making money versus looking over their children’s status and participation in school, resulted to a positive effect. As they looked back on their experiences of having to prioritize work over the activities of their children, they were surprised to know that as their children mature, they became more independent and can already stand on their own. Later, their children having to witness their everyday strife, were able to manage their own struggles in school that made them independent and now successfully working as professionals. Based on the lines 252-254; and 770-772:

And, [and---] being a part time, [you either have] no time, [or] less time for the children. But, my children are all trained to become survivor. [Hmm] kana na lang. Survivor manggud. (Mam-B, lines 252-254)

And, and---being a part time, no time, less time for the children but my children are all trained to become survivor. That’s it. Survivor—real survivor. (Mam-B, lines 252-254)

Kulang na rin yong time ko sa mga anak ko. Nagsariling sikap din ang mga anak. I also lack time for my children. (Mam-E, lines 770-772)

My children also strive hard on their own. (Mam-E, lines 770-772)

McGinn et al. (2015) even exposed in their study how one’s daughter or son’s self-reported happiness is not affected by being full-time employed of parents. They even emphasized that these children’s exposure to such kind of life can lead to an opportunity of a better future. Moreover, even if in the study of Kang et al. (2020), daughters of such career women wished a mother who are part time working for them, it is contrasting to

the fact that above children in the context of the participants are contented with the aspect of life support provided for them by such parents.

Sustaining the Roles

This theme signifies the facts of having to sustain the roles of a teacher-mother. Notwithstanding several laid challenges and hardships, living as such does not mean being into the negativities all alone. There are reasons why teacher-mothers remain to be one despite unplanned consequences and struggles they meet in this sphere.

Availing Benefits. The core idea of sustaining the roles reflects the self-assessment of the participants on the benefits of choosing to sustain fulfilling the role of full-time teacher. There are several reasons showing that being such one is beneficial. To mention, teacher-mothers are more available to attend to their own children who are studying in the same school they are assigned to. Financial stability is also a major consequence of being a teacher by profession. There is also an advantage for professional enhancements or development. Lastly, being self-reliant because of the aftermath of accomplishing several tasks while maintaining the welfare of children. In consequence, being a teacher in a school where your child is also a student is an advantage. She said:

In my part as a teacher, [ahh] there are advantages also. Like we are in the school with my little children—that is a privilege for me because we are in the same school. So, I can [ahh] look for her needs especially when [ahh] she felt [uhmm] kanang magsakit bitaw siya mam maglisod ko sa iyaha og atiman. Pero naa man lang mi sa isa ka school so dali dali lang nako siya maadtuan. Since I don't have [ahh] nanny at home. (Mam-A, lines 21-27)

In my part as a teacher, there are advantages also. Like we are in the school with my little children—that is a privilege for me because we are in the same school. So, I can look for her needs especially when she is sick, it is hard for me to nurse her. But, considering we are in the same school, I can quickly attend to her. (Mam-A, lines 21-27)

Financial stability is one of the advantages of being in such a career. Teacher-mothers prefer to work hard each day so as long as she provides for the welfare of her family. Mam-D even enunciated how she reciprocates loving her family through loving her job and doing it satisfactorily.

I have to priorities [prioritize]---[ahh] they said that [the] family is the first but for me, [ahh] because I love my [ahh] work--- I love my job, and also I love my family, but how can I love my family if [ahh] I will---[ahh] hindi ako magtrabaho nang maayos. Because [ahh], ang nabibigay ko sa family ko is galing sa job ko. So, I need to work hard for my job. (Mam-D, lines 646-649)

I love my job and also I love my family. But how can I love my family if I won't work properly. Because the things I provide for my family comes from my job. So, I need to work hard for my job. (Mam-D, lines 646-649)

Apparently, Mam-D's concept on supporting one's family through doing her job generously can best be compared to the study of Erdamar and Demirel (2016)

emphasizing the what comes before job satisfaction which is life satisfaction and work-family conflict. As to work-family conflict, however, it has been strategically surmounted by these participants with the mentality of survival and determination to succeed.

The reasons brought about by the participants are relatively comparable to the study of Hardin and Pennell (2022) indicating how teacher-mothers balance motherhood and work. That their informants were feeling empowered having to sustain working and family well-being specifically motherhood. Hence, these teacher-mothers are on the edge of strategizing balance from work-family conflict and performance of duty as they are admittable on the fact that being a teacher is generally having to encounter such. But, for a better future, life really must go on. One should not get discouraged and give up from various challenges and struggles in life or else, no future shall be tangibly fulfilling in the end.

Part time Mothers

Another heading that complements Table 1 is part time mother. In the context of our study, the essence of this term signifies the sacrifices of a teacher-mother by pouring all what is left of her after fulfilling the role as a full-time teacher. This section posits that teachers who are part time mothers are on the heights of perseverance behind all struggles (obvious and not) for family survival and preservation of one's profession.

Fulfilling the Roles

Combining career and motherhood is in fact an uneasy task. It takes so much effort and prioritization so that every expectation can be attended to in an evenhanded manner. In subsequence, it is inevitable that there are some responsibilities that will be off the grid in such a time when fulfilling roles are to be attended to, one by one.

Balancing Work and Family Responsibilities. This portion will take you to a different angle of how work and family is being attended to by teacher-mothers according to the context of my participants. In here, expositions on choosing between work or family is deemed inevitable. The reality is that a full-time teacher is likely to be above the umbrella of being a part-time mother. Nevertheless, flexibility of such career women is obviously being lived by as they opted to stay as is. Moving on, the reality of prerogatives selecting students versus own children in the context of being a full-time teacher opposes to what Stephens (2018) posits about having to choose part-time work so that one can participate in her own child's life. It is more on having to be effective as teachers especially to one's students to the extent of having to sacrifice time supposedly spent to own children. Moreover, Mam-F admitted that she imparts more of her knowledge to her students but not to her own child.

Uhm, yung kung full-time teacher [ahh], yung mga bata talaga, yung mga estudyante natuturuuan sila nang maayos. Pero sad to say, yung anak is medyo napapabayaan in terms sa pagfollow-up ng lesson ni --- lesson ng anak ko. Kasi nga [ahh]---pagdating sa bahay, you need to---to work yung mga household chores

doon and then pagod na, so wala ng time para sa anak. (Mam-F, lines 1222-1229)

...full-time teacher, the students are taught properly. But sad to say, that your own child is not attended much...in following-up the lesson of my child. Because, after arriving at home you need to work those household chores there and then tired already so, there's no more time for your child. (Mam-F, lines 1222-1229)

Majority of the participants are dealing with these challenges. However, having less time with their children according to Mam-B and Mam-E does not mean to have children who are misguided and rebellious persons as they mature. Instead, as these full-time teachers lived a life full of struggles, working like this meant having more time in school duties to the extent of bringing some at home, never stopped their children from being diligent and independent in school. In fact, their children managed to succeed in school and stood on their own until they finished college. Seemingly, this consequence is highly agreeable to what McGinn et al. (2015) proposed—stating that children who are exposed with stimulating experiences and personas are more likely to benefit from a better life's future.

The passion of such teacher-mother is highly appreciative. However, Baker (2021) said, performing to be a “good teacher” and a “good mother” may imply risks like mental health and more. Hence, there is an exposition Mam-E acquired sickness and risked her life because of health issues gotten from over work before. She said:

... at the end of the day, you're nothing. The output of your work is useless. I got lots of work. But it's useless. It gave me sickness. (Mam E, lines 1058-1064)

Surviving the Roles

At the end of the day, after all the workloads accomplished and time schedule attended, there is significantly a moment of survival—a moment of sigh and relief. Facing various struggles and challenges does not always connote surrender or hands off. In fact, it is like a constant lifestyle as a teacher-mother—to be able to encounter obstacles yet surmount them each day.

Strategizing. Taking several tasks and even accepting various roles that need to be attended to is hard. This is especially true whenever a person is in fact at the scenario of needing to choose which must be sacrificed so that one can attend to an obligation or responsibility. It takes a lot of strategizing and decision making of teacher-mothers for them to fulfill several roles that they are expected to accomplish or serve. According to the proposition of Rose (2017) about time pressure that goes by the aim for work efficacy and family well-being, these participants, too, reiterated the importance of having time management. Mam-D stated that:

“I should have a plan before that day on what to do so that I will not be cramming—both my career and my being a mother.” (lines 620-625)

Like Mam-C, Mam-D strategized looking after the school needs of her eldest daughter in high school through asking her husband to attend some meetings when she cannot make it. Even other participants, considering that each has different family backgrounds, relate themselves in the context full-time teacher and part time mother with having to sustain it

with time management. It is inevitable that teacher-mothers only have limited time during school days to attend to other roles outside being teachers. Even break times are clocked and so the focus during these days is more on school works and pupils, of course. Notwithstanding the fact that these career women are indulging most of their time in work, yet there is still a pinhole to which one can pass through to make up with one's other responsibility---particularly, meeting the needs of own child.

During weekdays, kulang man jud akong time, weekends, bawi bawi pud mi weekends—we have our bonding ana tapos didto na nako maopen iyang kung unsa ilang assignments may mga projects ba. (Mam-A, lines 42-27)

Considering I have less time during weekdays, I make it up during weekends—we have our bonding and then I can open/figure out their assignments or do they have projects. (Mam-A, lines 42-27)

While Mam-A makes it up on weekends, Mam-F who happened to be a widow, other than weekends, strategized spending even a small amount of time left for her after school days and spend it on communicating with her son.

So, [ahh] for me, kung may time talaga kahit 30 minutes nabibigay ko yun kay Clark. For example, pag-uwi ko, so kung may time pa ako na kaya pa ng katawan ko, I give 30 minutes for Clark na magfollow-up sa lesson niya and then Saturday [ahh] and Sunday, kung may vacant time, so doon ko inaasikaso lahat ng needs niya. And, of course, pagdating sa bahay, kailangan kausapin talaga yung anak para kung ano yung pangangailangan niya sa school para aware din ako. Kasi nga wala akong time sa morning—kasi lahat ng time sa morning and afternoon nandoon lahat sa school. (Mam-F, lines 1262-1273)

So, for me, if there is time really, even 30 minutes, I can give it to Clark. For example, when I get home, so if I still have time and my body is still able, I give 30 minutes for Clark to follow up his lessons and then Saturday ahh and Sunday, if there is vacant time, so there I attend all of his needs. And, of course, when I get home, there is a need to talk with your child so to know what his needs are in school so I should be aware too. It's because I don't have time in the morning—because all of the time in the morning and afternoon are all in school. (Mam-F, lines 1262-1273)

This set-up lived-by these participants are living testimonies which agree to Rose (2017) who said that career woman surely encounters time pressure as she aims for work efficacy an maintain family well-being. Relatively, based on these teacher-mothers, it is indeed that time is too limited with such a career. Hence, the positive consequence of not being present sometimes to one's child's activities or needs, I should say, teacher-mothers see to is that the foreign are provided and supported with, financially, emotionally, and morally. This reality does not so agreeing to Dotti Sani's (2022) findings that state, the side of having more time taking care of children and even satisfaction in life are on those employed full-time. However, in his statement regarding life satisfaction, I can attest that it is true. On the other hand, Mam-B's statement on explaining the situation and supporting her children is as follows:

“... what I did is for the family. So, I already explain to my children that what will happen if I'm--- I'm a full-time mother.” (lines 302-304)

To support this statement, Mam-B is trying to say that she is living in a hustle most of her time as a teacher, that she could not attend most of her children's needs and this situation is a part of her strife for the welfare of the family.

Planning

This main theme emphasizes the ability to think ahead about what you will do for the incoming days. Basically, planning, since then is perceived to be the first course to be accomplished whenever you want to start something and finish it successfully. In the context of my study, planning is one of the factors that made teacher-mothers beat the hustle they encounter inevitably.

Avoiding Cramming. This part reveals knowing how to plan for precedented activities. Apart from that, this section also shall give an eye opening as to how teacher-mothers are lessening the bulks they are shouldering. Hence, several statements relating to the core idea presented are exposed here. Time management is the only one consistent even if phases of life change progressively as time goes by. Ever since, in whichever events in life, it is said that time management resolves the hecticness of schedules. Accordingly, Soelistiyono and Chuan (2023) found out that career women find ways to give time for work and family. Moreso, when it comes to emergencies and health-related issues to be attended, the priority is on the needs of the family over work obligations and responsibilities. However, there is an edge with teacher-mothers as they can depend on their husbands (who are self-employed or employed outside the government and whose schedules are flexible) on the matters of attending their children's needs—important events in schools. Hence, a supporting statement of Mam-D exposed that while she plans on what to do, she also has her husband to substitute in attending their children's school activities whenever she cannot make it. She said:

Siguro [ahh]--[sa sina--] what I've said later [earlier] na dapat ahead of time I have a plan kung ano ba yung dapat unahin, kung ano ba yung dapat i-priority or kung saan ba yung mas importante kay kung, [ahh---]kung 'di naman ganoon ka importante [sa ba] ---being mother, [ahh] unahin ko muna yung work ko kung pwede namang [my ahh]---halimbawa my husband siya muna ang mag-attend ng ibang mga [ahh] meetings--- or any occasions na related sa mga anak ko. (Mam-D, lines 655-663)

Maybe...as what I've said later that ahead of time I have a plan on what to do first if what should be prioritized or which is more important... If it is not really that important in being mother, ahh I'll prioritize first my work, if it can be ahh...for example, for the meantime, my husband may attend to several ahh meetings, or any occasions that are related to my children. (Mam-D, lines 655-663)

Mam-C also exposed the matters relating to having a husband who can assist or say look over needs to be attended to on her behalf.

Wa pay pagmahay [nga kuwaan] kay kung [ang] sa balay, wala koy problema [sa kung ano]. Naa lang man akong darling. (Mam-C, lines 439-441)

I still have no regrets because when it comes to household, I have no problem. My darling is there. (Mam-C, lines 439-441)

Mam-C's statement refers to her response with the household chores to do as part of her being a housewife too. Her next statements hereafter refer to balancing her roles and on how she prioritizes instances over work obligations.

"Because when there are important events, like...birthday or Christmas like that, we also have gathering that I also give...yes, priorities." (lines 542-547)

"...whichever who needed most...For example if my kid will get sick, I will choose her." (lines 584-586)

The expositions laid are agreeing to that of the study of Nam and Sennott (2023) depicting the effect of aspirations of women when they are expected to be the sole caregiver of children than that of the other way around. They posit that there is less of an aspiration for work when women (by gender role) connote to be the only one to attend to their children. Obviously, in the context of my participants, they can work with less hassle of attending children's needs because they have partners to substitute for them. In addition, some of the statements implying the thought of applying time management to maintain work-life balance say:

"I learned that time management is needed. So, we can give attention to others...we could spare them a part of attention." (Mam-C, lines 561-566)

"So, I learned that I need to manage my time effectively. I need to have time management, that's the most important thing that time... the time, the needs of my child is not left unattended. At the same time, I don't get to leave unattended the responsibilities of mine as a teacher." (Mam-F, lines 1296-1301)

These testimonies relate to what Rose (2017) found out that career woman surely encounters time pressures as she aims for work efficacy and maintain family well-being. But I believe this time pressure today is beaten mostly by teacher-mothers because there is already a mindset that once you entered such career, it inevitably allies challenges. And one of those is as complex as having to handle time pressures. Nevertheless, there is resilience, positivity and life goals that lead teacher-mothers to take each path efficiently in balance.

Revitalizing the Persona

In the context of my study, signifies recharging of oneself after a long day. Teacher-mothers' every day journey is not generalized as going well as planned. There are unexpected events wherein one's energy should be doubled as events and workloads may ally rushing of time. Subsequently, pausing from the hustle of the public sphere and going into revitalization is undeniably a help.

Strengthening Faith in God. When life is complex and living is almost wrapped up with fast changing technology that we should cope-up to, there is still room for ideologies. Faith keeps us live at ease. Faith gives us hope. And faith helps us think all trials are surmountable. Hence, it is through keeping the faith that Mam-E survived her hardships before and during her teacher-mother role. Even after going off from her marriage which supposedly made her free, yet she found it hard in times that she is sick—that no one was there to look for her and attend to her needs, too. It is through faith that now she

manages to go on despite her health issues. It is one of her reasons for maintaining work-life balance especially that she admitted and realized she has been living a stressed-out life.

Diyos ko. Oh, ang hirap. As single mom, na magkasakit ka...Wala ka gung...Wala kang matawag. Yong magsakit ka--- Kahit maghilot o magpa-init lang ng tubig, o magbigay ng pagkain mo kasi gutom ka na, hilong hilo ka na, paano mo yan balansehin? May school ka pa na kailangang pumasok. Kay mag-absent ka na ayaw mo mang mag-absent... kay [kasi] ayaw mo siyang---bawasan ang sweldo para sa mga anak mo yun. Kasi yung sweldo mo para sa mga anak mo yun. Paano ko gibalanse [binalanse]? Hindi ko rin napansin nakayanan kong ibalanse yun. 'Pag may problema ako, paano ko balansehin yung buhay ko, kasi mabigat na e...Nandon sa simbahan. Nagtuturok ako ng kandila. (Mam-E, lines 970-1000)

My God...Oh, so hard. As single mom, that you get sick...there's nobody you...there's nobody you can call...even to massage...or heat some water...or hand you food because your already hungry, you're too dizzy...how will you balance? Then you still have school? You still have to go to school. Because if you will be absent that you don't want to be absent so it would not...it will deduct from you...It will deduct from your salary which for your children...Because your salary is for your children how did I balance? I didn't notice that I was able to balance it...when I have a problem, how do I balance my life, it's too heavy already? ...it's in the church...I light a candle. (Mam-E, lines 970-1000)

Moreover, faith in God covers all negativities with hope and ease that we continue to go on in life. In fulfilling our being a full-time teacher and part time mother, faith can keep us "alive". More so, in the experiences shared forth by Mam-E on the lights she saw from faith that held her strong despite the "darkness" in her life before. She learned that through having faith in God led her to balance her dual or multiple roles is.

Una [una], faith kay God. Strong faith. Pangalawa, ikaw mismo sa sarili mo, alamin mo kung ano yung kakayanan mo. Yun yong kaya mo. 'Pag hindi mo na kaya (if you cannot make it), then be it. Lax, hindi ko kaya to. Hanggang 'dun ka na lang. Tanggapin mo kung---'Wag mong abuting na ano...Kasi pag-inabot mo na hindi mo kaya... [Makuntento ka mam Nica.] Contentment din yan siya. Tapos pa'no mo balansehin yun, focus ka sa kung ano yung aim mo. (Mam-E, lines 1082-1100)

First, faith kay God. Second, you yourself, think of your ability...that's what you are able of. If you cannot make it, then be it. 'Lax, I can't do this. You're until there only. Because if you reach something you cannot...be contented. It is also contentment. Then how will you balance it?... focus on your aim. (Mam-E, lines 1082-1100)

Based on the statements of Mam-E, it can be implied that her insights are really reliable. It shows how she was strategizing her life to maintain work-life balance. The flow of her life ventures can best be compared to the findings of Galili (2020) elucidating the efforts of teacher-mothers in maintaining family wellbeing despite several expectations and/or tasks inevitably shouldered by her from outside her private sphere. On the other hand, Mam-E's experiences contradict to that of the proposition of Nam and Sennott (2023) which explains that when a mother is expected to shoulder all the needs of her children, caregiving in particular, she rather diverts herself on aspiring in her career to rearing her children. Because it is of the same reason (her children's wellbeing) that Mam-E stayed being a career woman.

Continuing the Passion

Passion is certainty. Passion is love. When there is passion, there is perseverance and optimism. Even joy, allies passion. Passion is committing to make a choice out of love and sincerity. Nevertheless, this does not mean positivity in all aspects every time. It will always come a time of testing how tough and firm someone in doing what you love and for the best of it. However, my participants' trials have never been an obstacle for them to continue their passion on teaching and sustaining life of a mother, simultaneously. Their chosen career is their passion and obviously this conquers every day challenges they encounter.

Loving What They Do. They say, love conquers all. Relatively, loving what you do lightens the load of your work or tasks. I can even attest to this. If you enjoy and love whatever you do, it seems that your day is not really that tiring and hard. It is even more engaging and stimulating. In subsequence, Mam-D's statement about this says:

“...is just continue loving your work and then everything will follow [na---and then ahh] because [ahh-] that is [im---] that is very important [is] you love what you are doing everyday..” (lines 669-671)

The proposition of Mam-D, however, opposes to the fact of the parallelism between being a full time mother and family wellbeing as attested with the statement of Abillar and Florida (2019) exposing the fact that full-time mothers are moving heaven and earth purposively for the betterment of each member of the family, The full-time mothers in their family pursuits were likely to pursue certain goals which strengthen each family member.

On the other hand, on the matters of fulfilling each role all because of the love for family, there must also be communication. Explaining is a communication which aim is to make the receiver of it understand the situation or reasons of issues—or anything. I also believe that this key is effective purposively to make children of such career women understand why sometimes not all plans and even commitments of their teacher-mothers with them fails because of work reasons.

Nevertheless, there are positive consequences of not being present sometimes to one's child's activities or needs, I should say. Teacher-mothers see to it that the foreign are provided and supported with—financially, emotionally, and morally. This reality does not so agreeing to Dotti Sani's (2022) findings that state, the side of having more time taking care of children and even satisfaction in life are on those employed full-time. However, in his statement regarding life satisfaction, I can attest that it is true. On the other hand, Mam-B's statement on explaining the situation and supporting her children is as follows:

“... what I did is for the family. So, I already explain to my children nga [that] what will happen if I'm--- I'm a full-time mother..” (lines 302-304)

To support this statement, Mam-B is trying to say that she is living in a hustle most of her time as a teacher, that she could not attend most of her children's needs and this situation is a part of her strife for the welfare of the family.

Finding Recreation

Recreation, in this context, meant something or someone that takes you away from loneliness and detours you to being simply happy and contented. It agrees to the saying, “no man is an island”. Consequently, teacher-mothers are also into going in their public spheres to divert themselves from living a stationary life under the context of their professions.

Bonding with Friends. When you are down and preoccupied with bulk of work, it is unnecessary to continue being such. Take a break. Halt the hassle and go to your comfort zone then recharge. Work is there. Accomplishing one task does not mean ending all your tasks in one day even if you are already worn out. One will go then another shall arrive. It is the nature of work. It is the constant of life especially to teacher-mothers. Giroux (2019) found out that if teachers continue to be stressed out, it may affect their resilience—obviously leaving them unfocused and less functional in school and at home, probably. However, Mam-E strategically chose to find stress relievers to help her lighten her burdens.

Conclusions

Conclusively, living as a full-time teachers meant challenges. However, each challenging roles should be attended in accordance to level of priority. And, living as a full time teacher also meant availing benefits from ones department. On the other hand, being a part time mother meant having to balance work and family responsibilities, as well. It also allies strategizing to attend each life roles. Further, these propositions exposed are in affirmation of the Role-balance theory which signifies that work-life can be maintained if each role shall be given attention in an evenhanded fashion. It also implies that there is no need to struggle in attending to work-life if you know how to distribute your time to tasks or things you need to do.

Recommendations

This part reflects recommendations to improve the significance of this study. It posits several suggestions that may enhance the system of work among affected teacher-mothers. Rest assured that all propositions are brought out from the expositions made by the participants through thorough data analysis and systematic standardization of the whole study.

As researchers, it may help to know how the situation differs when sample size is increased and on the context of teacher-fathers, too. It would be a gain of knowledge and fact finding on how these kinds of participants deal with such roles. It may contribute to

persuading some changes in the work system if the findings of such study is agreeing to ours.

Further, to other studies and future researches, a bigger sample population is recommended for a more clearer picture of the issue on teacher-mothers lived experiences and maintaining work-life balance. It shall then be empirical to review some system adjustments in the context of teaching loads and other ancillary services. Further, a bigger sample population for future researches may also lead to a more convincing facts on the experiences lived by teacher-mothers in this era.

Compliance with Ethical Standards

This research observed all ethical considerations prescribed by Holy Trinity College so that actions that may implicitly or explicitly affect or exploit individuals involved in the study be avoided. It includes sets of essential standards to ensure validity and reliability of our study. These are informed consent, voluntary participation, gender sensitivity, culture sensitivity, data privacy act, and health safety protocol. Hence, it was important to give my participants a background information and get briefed on the how's and why's of the study. It was in fact a responsibility that these teacher-mothers were well-informed of their freedom to indulge or reject it, and, made sure that we were entrusted with the data conservation they willingly shared with us, and we held ourselves responsible for any grudges it may result in.

Also, we adapted some considerations according to the citation of Anwar (2015). It discussed that research participants should not be subjected to harm in any ways whatsoever; (b) respect the dignity of research participants should be prioritised; and (c) full consent should be obtained from the participants prior to the study. Thus, we received a positive response of affirmation from the participants. We fully understood, on the other hand, one rejection appertaining to the individualized interview we told them to happen that meant spending and sparing from their hectic time schedule. Nevertheless, it was heart-warming to be considered by these six participants who agreed to contribute and participate until the completion of this study.

Moreover, a bit of advice from Perni et al. (2022) proposing that we should entail common understanding with our participants implies a give and take situation in which their voluntary participation is reciprocated through full information in advance without any coercion or whatsoever that deprives their right of not participating freely (Perni et al., 2022). Hence, we ensured that in every meeting with the participants allied proper coordination, comfortable environment, and ease of expressing their thoughts. On the matters of data privacy and conservation, we took responsibility in ensuring confidentiality to any personal data and information my participants willingly shared with me. We ensured the participants that they will be described anonymously so their personal information is secured and protected. Significantly, it includes the intention to protect the

personal data and views of these participants. Hence, we made sure that all personal information of my participants was taken to full confidentiality.

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